

Review Guidelines for Coscine DataStorage.nrw Resources

Guidance and explanation for the review of submitted storage space applications

Authors:

Katja Jansen¹ (ORCID: 0009-0005-7076-9848), Ilona Lang¹ (ORCID: 0000-0002-7202-5982), Michèle Robrecht¹ (ORCID: 0000-0002-1949-0009), Katharina Grünwald¹ (ORCID: 0000-0001-7550-552X), Lukas C. Bossert¹ (ORCID: 0000-0003-3076-3968), Marcel Nellesen¹ (ORCID: 0000-0002-1830-5780), Marius Politze¹ (ORCID: 0000-0003-3175-0659), Katharina Koch² (ORCID: 0000-0002-7455-2874), Elena Schick³ (ORCID: 0000-0002-2621-4133), Andreas Schramm³ (ORCID: 0000-0002-6245-2809), Michael Werger⁴ (ORCID: 0009-0001-8756-8955).

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¹ RWTH Aachen University

² Hochschule Bochum

³ Ruhr University Bochum

⁴ Universität Duisburg-Essen

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1 Preamble

Coscine⁵ (**C**ollaborative **S**cientific **I**ntegration **E**nvironment) is a research data management platform that enables researchers to manage research (meta)data. The platform has been developed at RWTH Aachen University since 2018 as an open-source platform in accordance with the FAIR principles (Lang et al. 2025) and provides access to and management of research data from a research project. Coscine is offered to DH.NRW universities as “software as a service.” Within the framework of Coscine.nrw, DataStorage.nrw is also connected as a resource type and provisioned via Coscine.

DataStorage.nrw is a redundant S3 object storage system operated at four DH.NRW university locations: RWTH Aachen University, University of Duisburg-Essen, University of Paderborn, and University of Cologne. DataStorage.nrw is part of the DH.NRW storage infrastructure and thus supports the implementation of the state concept RDM of the state initiative for research data management - fdm.nrw. The object storage solution has been designed to accommodate particularly large amounts of data that need to be stored long-term, with a capacity of up to 24 petabytes. Storage space resources are managed for Coscine using the JARDS software. A separate Coscine JARDS instance (Coscine-JARDS) was developed for this purpose in July 2023⁶. Storage space applications for DataStorage.nrw are evaluated by RDM staff at DH.NRW universities in a peer review process. The following criteria, which were established for the allocation of storage space in the DataStorage.nrw application, are taken into account as far as possible:

*“The aim is to use a low-threshold offering that starts at the data collection stage to bridge the gap between the earliest possible point in the research workflow for the structured collection of data and the **metadata describing** it, and specialist and community repositories such as those in the NFDI, thereby contributing to compliance with good scientific practice.” [...]*

*“The technical provision should be accompanied by a **science-led management process**. This process, which is linked to the same process in the field of national high-performance computing (NHR), has also been tested with FD-storage and as part of the RDS.NRW project, and is to be further expanded as part of the project described here. This includes in particular:*

*Project-based application for storage resources, evaluation of **applications via a science-led process (blind peer review)** by a pool of reviewers from all user institutions, and provisioning of storage resources.”⁷*

These review guidelines are intended to serve as a reference for all reviewers of Coscine storage space applications for DataStorage.nrw resources, to help them evaluate the above criteria. During the Coscine.nrw user meeting on April 29, 2025, RDM staff and data stewards from North Rhine-

⁵ <https://about.coscine.de/> (accessed on January, 12th, 2026)

⁶ Coscine-JARDS (accessed on January, 12th, 2026)

⁷ Excerpt from the DataStorage.nrw application “NRW FD Storage – Application in the Large Equipment Program of the Federal States” (accessed on January, 12th, 2026)

Westphalia discussed the criteria for allocating storage space. These discussions formed the basis for the curation recommendation and review guidelines.

This document covers aspects of data assessment relevant to Coscine and DataStorage.nrw. Additionally, it discusses the assessment process (technical and scientific review) of storage space applications, including text modules for queries to applicants. These text modules serve as aids for communication with researchers at the home organization (via email or personal consultation) and can be adopted or adapted as needed for specific statements in the storage space application. In the case of rejection, applicants must be provided with detailed and meaningful feedback from the reviewers. As part of the review process, reviewers must enter the relevant feedback, including suggestions for improvement, under “Feedback for the applicant.”

The order of the chapters follows the sequence of questions within a storage space application. Finally, there is an assessment checklist to help reviewers assess storage space applications. A detailed description of the organizational process for assessing storage space applications by DH.NRW universities can be found in the Coscine documentation.⁸

The curation recommendations and review guidelines presented here will be discussed regularly at future basic training courses, monthly consultation hours and user meetings of Coscine.nrw, and expanded with new versions if necessary.

2. Aspects of data review

2.1 Confidentiality of reviewers

To ensure confidentiality, only reviewers assigned by the coordination office may access the relevant application and carry out the associated review. No content may be forwarded to third parties. To ensure a fair review process that complies with the guidelines, random checks are carried out by the service management team at FDSI.nrw⁹.

2.2 Coscine-JARDS

JARDS (Joint Application, Review, and Dispatch Service) is a software designed and used for the allocation of computing time or storage and data processing resources. Since July 2023, Coscine has been using its own JARDS instance (Coscine-JARDS) for the allocation of storage resources, thereby creating a basis for the allocation processes for storage resources on DataStorage.nrw. Coscine-JARDS can be used to submit storage space applications for various resource types in Coscine (see below) and then have them reviewed by the RDM staff at DH.NRW universities.

2.3 Resource types

Coscine offers researchers a representation of their project structure for managing access permissions and research (meta)data. By integrating various services, known as resources,

⁸ Storage-Reviewer - Documentation Coscine (accessed on January, 12th, 2026)

⁹ <https://www.fdm.nrw/forschungsdatenspeicherinfrastruktur> (accessed on January, 12th, 2026)

researchers can view and manage all project data in one place via the Coscine web interface. In addition to storage resources, Linked Data and GitLab resources are also integrated via Coscine, but these are not reviewed by Coscine.nrw. There are different resource types (web, S3, and WORM) for DataStorage.nrw storage resources, which meet the different needs of researchers for managing their research data.

The following section describes the different resource types available from DataStorage.nrw and how to apply for them.

2.3.1 Web

The web resource type is used for storing small amounts of data, such as survey results. Web resources can only be accessed via the Coscine web interface or REST API. This means that the metadata management system provided by Coscine must be used when uploading data, and the appropriate metadata profile must be selected. Data can only be uploaded if the mandatory fields of the selected metadata profile have been completed. Researchers can choose from metadata profiles of varying scope, extend them using the metadata profile generator, or create new ones.

For DataStorage.nrw, authorised university employees are provided with 100 GB of storage space per project for web resources as standard. Storage space beyond this must be requested via a storage space application in Coscine-JARDS.

2.3.2 S3

S3 resources¹⁰ provide direct access to the Coscine storage system (DataStorage.nrw in this case) and can be used to store and manage large amounts of data, for example. They can also be mounted in other systems, offering a high degree of flexibility in the research process. Accessing the stored data is preferably done via S3 clients (e.g. Cyberduck), but it can also be done via the web interface or the REST API. This enables the metadata management offered by Coscine to be utilized via metadata profiles; however, this is not enforced when uploading directly via the S3 interface. Researchers can choose from metadata profiles of varying scope, extend them using the metadata profile generator or create new ones themselves. However, metadata management can also be implemented using proprietary methods. These must be clearly explained in the application. An application for storage space for the S3 resource type must always be submitted via Coscine-JARDS.

2.3.3 WORM

WORM (**W**rite **O**nce, **R**ead **M**any) resources are available for storing research data requiring a high level of protection in terms of immutability. Once uploaded, files stored in this resource type cannot be modified or deleted. Access to the data is equivalent to that of the S3 resource type ([see section 2.2.2, 'S3'](#)). In addition to non-enforced metadata management, the WORM resource type entails high responsibility for uploaded files as deletion is not possible (e.g. with regard to personal data). Therefore, a storage space application via Coscine-JARDS is always required in this case and is the most extensive one.

2.4 Allocation of storage

Storage space applications are submitted, reviewed and allocated via Coscine-JARDS. The number and depth of questions asked for applications of different resource types in Coscine differ based on

¹⁰ S3 (Simple Storage Service) is a simple object storage interface for data that supports fast retrieval of object data.

varying degrees of freedom in metadata management. Applicants who commit to recording metadata in accordance with the profiles provided by Coscine have to answer fewer detailed questions.

Each storage space application undergoes a technical review first. During this review, we check whether the planned use of the resources allows for the long-term reusability of the data. This includes technical aspects such as the size and number of individual files, the selected file formats, and the organization of the data and its annotation. These aspects are necessary for compliance with the FAIR principles.

Two technical reviews are initially conducted: one by the RDM responsible person at the university where the application was submitted, and one by the RDM responsible person at a different DH.NRW university. If the two reviews reach different conclusions, a third review from a different university will be conducted.

Applications for storage space exceeding 125 TB must also undergo scientific review (see section 4, 'Scientific Review'). The scientific quality of the project can be demonstrated through an external scientific review of the originating research project. Alternatively, the coordination office at RWTH Aachen University will organize the review.

Once a storage space application has been approved, the coordination office at RWTH Aachen University will allocate the storage space to the project, including any optional subprojects. If the application is rejected, applicants receive feedback from the reviewers to assist them in resubmitting the application (major revision). The possible scenarios for the results of a storage space application are shown in Table 1. Applicants may resubmit their application a maximum of two times. Each time an application is resubmitted, it is reviewed again by the previous reviewers.

Table 1: Possible scenarios for the results of a storage space request

Technical Review				Scientific Review (>125 TB)	
Home	External 1	External 2	Result	External Researcher	Result
+	+	/	Allocation	+	Allocation
+	-	-	Rejection	/	Rejection
-	/	/	Rejection	/	Rejection

Key: “+” stands for a positive assessment, “-” for a negative assessment, “/” for an assessment that is not required.

2.5 Test Projects

The RDM staff at DH.NRW universities undergo basic training with Coscine Service Management based on the train-the-trainer principle. This training covers both Coscine support and the assessment of storage space applications. As part of this training, each DH.NRW university has received a test project comprising five sub-projects, as well as the option to create web and S3 resources. RDM staff at the universities can independently issue and manage these sub-projects to researchers for testing the functions. Storage space for WORM resources is not issued, as the functions correspond to S3 resources and only the subsequent storage on DataStorage.nrw is permanent. RDM staff members are assigned the 'owner' role in the test projects and create web and S3 resources for the test users. The RDM staff then add test users to one of the test projects as members.

The RDM staff require the following information from the test users:

- Email addresses of all test users
- Number of resources required (e.g. 1 web resource and 1 S3 resource)
- Quota for each resource (max. 100 GB for web or S3 resources)
- Metadata profile(s) to be used for resources.

Instructions for the RDM staff on how to handle test projects can also be found in the documentation¹¹.

3. Technical Review

Storage space applications with a maximum quota of 125 TB are subject to a technical review by RDM staff. Storage space requests exceeding 125 TB also require a scientific review (see section 4, 'Scientific review'). The review checklist only lists the mandatory items required for a successful application.

The following is a detailed overview of the information required from applicants for the technical review.

3.1 Contact information

Regardless of the type of resource, Coscine-JARDS applications begin with the entry of the applicant's contact information. The coordination office at RWTH Aachen University then checks whether the storage space application was submitted by a researcher at a DH.NRW university, or if support from an NFDI consortium is guaranteed (see section 3.2). Applications clearly assigned to a university are forwarded directly to a reviewer at that university. If no DH.NRW university is directly involved, the coordination office at RWTH Aachen University checks for an NFDI connection. If one is found, this is noted as a comment in the application, after which two independent DH.NRW universities are assigned to review it. The reviewers are assigned by the coordination office at RWTH Aachen University.

3.1.1 Status of applicants

When submitting a Coscine-JARDS application, it is mandatory to specify the principal investigator (PI) and person of contact (PC). It is possible to enter the same person as both the PI and the PC. Ideally, both the PI and PC should be available long term to enable long-term access to the research project, in accordance with the FAIR principles. The PI is responsible for the project. This is typically the role of professors. Reviewers must check that the PI's status is sufficient. People who apply for storage space for their thesis (e.g. bachelor's, master's or doctoral thesis) are not eligible to apply as PI.

¹¹ Quota test projects - Documentation Coscine (accessed on January, 12th, 2026)

Text Module

Upon reviewing the person you entered as the Principal Investigator (PI), it does not appear that they are available for the research project on a long-term basis. We therefore ask you to resubmit the application with a PI who meets these criteria and is employed as a postdoctoral researcher or professor, for example. Otherwise, please provide an explanation of the PI you have entered and their role within the research project.

3.2 Project information

Project information is available for all resource types and must be checked according to the following criteria

3.2.1 URL

The URL of the Coscine project must be provided in order to allocate storage space. Therefore, at this point, it is necessary to check whether the provided URL leads to a Coscine project. If not, the URL must be requested from the applicants; otherwise, RWTH Aachen University will not be able to allocate storage space if the application is approved. If the URL leads to the PID contact page of the Coscine project, the check is successful.

Text Module

The URL provided in the storage space application does not correspond to a Coscine project. Please send us the URL of your Coscine project to which the request refers. If you are requesting quotas for several projects, please provide a list of all the relevant URLs and the storage space amounts required for each one.

Example: Total quota = 50 TB

<https://coscine.rwth-aachen.de/p/testprojekt> = 20 TB

https://coscine.rwth-aachen.de/p/unterprojekt_a = 20 TB

https://coscine.rwth-aachen.de/p/unterprojekt_b = 10 TB

3.2.2 Project relevance

The key question for reviewers is: 'Is the storage space request based on a research project?'. One criterion for allocating DataStorage.nrw resources is that storage must be requested for a specific project. Reviewers must therefore assess whether the title, funding numbers (e.g. DFG or European Horizon) and/or abstract clearly indicate that the storage space request is for a scientific research project. The project may be about to start (up to three months in advance), ongoing, or completed (archiving). Indications of a clear project reference include:

- Defined project start and end dates

- A clear research question addressed
- Funding numbers refer to the research project described
- **No** requests for storage space for an entire institute (at least the subprojects must have an individual project reference).
- **No** storage space applications for data exclusively related to teaching or administration.

In the storage space application, researchers must also specify the discipline to which the research project can be assigned. This information is used for anonymized reporting purposes and will be used for allocating a scientific review for storage space applications of more than 125 TB, for example (see [section 4, 'Scientific review'](#)).

Text Module

When reviewing your application for storage space, it is unclear whether there is a specific project reference, and if so, what it is. Therefore, please specify which research project the storage space is required for. Please note that storage space provisioned via Coscine can only be allocated if a project reference is provided. For example, it is not possible to allocate storage space for an entire institute.

3.2.3 NFDI Association

see [section 3.1, Contact Information](#).

3.3 Storage Space

The queries in the Coscine-JARDS section *Storage Space* are not available for all resource types to the same extent. The criteria described below specify the resource types for which the check is performed.

3.3.1 Scope

Resource types: all

Researchers must specify how much storage space is required for their research project in their application. This information is entered in Coscine-JARDS in gigabytes (GB).

The key question for reviewers is: 'Is the amount of storage space requested proportionate to the project description?'

Indicators of a balanced relationship between storage space and project description include:

- The file formats and amount of storage space specified are consistent (e.g. not 125 TB of storage space for small text documents)
- Estimated information on the number and size of files generated/to be generated for the research project

- Information on file types and quantities can also provide clues for a realistic assessment of the requested storage space (see below).

Text Module

When reviewing your storage space application, the reviewers noticed that the amount of storage space requested does not correspond to the project description. Please provide a description of the file formats, sizes and quantities of files that are expected or have already been generated during the implementation of your project. This information will help the reviewers in their assessment

3.3.2 Related subprojects

Resource types: all

Quota is allocated on a project basis in Coscine, i.e. storage space cannot currently be inherited hierarchically. Therefore, all Coscine projects relevant to the research project that require storage space must be listed in the storage space application. It is important that:

- All projects and subprojects have been created in Coscine, and the corresponding URLs have been specified. Otherwise, the quota admins at RWTH Aachen University will not be able to allocate storage space.
- The total amount of storage space allocated to individual projects must equal the total quota requested.

Text Module

In Coscine, storage space is allocated on a project basis, which means that all projects to which quotas are to be allocated must be listed in the storage space application. The total storage space requested for individual projects must correspond to the total quota requested. Unfortunately, the information in your application is unclear in this regard and important information necessary for allocating storage space is missing. We therefore ask you to provide a list as shown in the example below. Example:

Total quota = 50 TB

<https://coscine.rwth-aachen.de/p/testproject> = 20 TB

https://coscine.rwth-aachen.de/p/subproject_a = 20 TB

https://coscine.rwth-aachen.de/p/subproject_b = 10 TB

3.3.3 File types

Resource types: all

Coscine can be used to store a wide variety of data types (e.g. text, audio, video, graphics, and other binary files) on DataStorage.nrw resources (e.g. web, S3, WORM). This information may help to evaluate the storage space requirements mentioned above.

3.3.4 File sizes

Resource types: all

Coscine can be used to store a wide variety of file sizes on DataStorage.nrw resources (web, S3 and WORM). This information can provide clues for evaluating the selected resource type and the specified storage space requirements. It may also be helpful to question the completeness of the data. For example, in scientific simulations, can all the necessary input data be identified, and are they described in a way that ensures reproducibility? Are code references available?

3.3.5 Personal data

Resource types: all

In principle, the storage of personal data on the DataStorage.nrw storage system is not excluded. However, users are responsible for checking whether their specific research data can be stored on the storage systems and what additional security measures are required. This query serves as a reminder to researchers to investigate this matter further. No direct action or inquiry is required on the part of the assessors, but they can recommend counselling by RDM staff or the data protection or security officer at the home institution if necessary.

3.3.6 Metadata profile

Resource types: all

In accordance with the FAIR principles, the submission of metadata for the respective research data is crucial for the use of DataStorage.nrw resources. Important questions for reviewers at this stage are: Is a metadata profile used in Coscine? If so, which one? Are the mandatory fields of this metadata profile sufficient for the requested storage space? Is it a subject-specific metadata profile? Does the metadata profile specify rich metadata (i.e. bibliographic, administrative or technical)? Generic statements such as 'Metadata is provided in accordance with FAIR principles' are not sufficient.

3.3.7 Reasons for using cosine

Resource types: all

At DataStorage.nrw, all the reasons for use listed in the application (single-choice question) are permitted. The reason provided will only be used for assessment purposes and, if necessary, for further consultation.

Digression: Metadata and metadata profiles in Coscine

Coscine allows metadata to be stored at different levels. Metadata must be entered when creating a project or resource. Furthermore, regardless of whether the web interface or API is used, files can only be uploaded within a web resource after metadata has been entered. Metadata profiles are used to enter metadata in this way. Researchers can create these profiles and reuse them. However, when using S3 resources, it is possible to circumvent the mandatory entry of metadata, as direct access to the storage system is possible via S3 clients. For this reason, applicants must clearly state in storage space application for S3 resource types whether and to what extent metadata storage is guaranteed. Therefore, the question of entering meaningful and rich metadata is a key criterion in the approval or rejection of an S3 storage.

Text Module

In terms of the FAIR principles, the storage of metadata relating to research data is a core aspect of Coscine. However, your storage space application does not specify exactly how metadata relating to your research data will be stored. To give the reviewers a deeper insight into your (planned) metadata management, please describe the following points:

- At which points in the project will metadata be collected and stored?
- Is a metadata profile from Coscine already being used? Has a separate metadata profile been created? If so, please provide the merge request [9] and the profile name. Please also give a brief explanation of why you chose this metadata profile.
- If the application was submitted for S3: Please describe in detail the workflow for storing metadata. Have you automated any (sub)steps for this, e.g., using a script?

If you have a diagram of the metadata storage workflow in the proposed project, please feel free to attach it.

3.3.8 WORM

Resource types: WORM

The WORM resource type enables the storage of research data requiring a high level of protection against manipulation. To reduce the risk of storage resources being wasted due to incorrect use, the storage space application for this resource type contains additional questions compared to applications for the web or S3 resource types (see below). These questions are intended to ensure that researchers are aware of the potential implications. If the need for the WORM resource type is justified, the storage space request will be reviewed by experts from the researcher's home organization and another university, as is the case with other resource types.

No text modules are provided for this resource type, as a consultation is always required. Researchers can submit an application for WORM resources without first having a consultation. However, in this case, a meeting with the RDM staff of the home organization must take place after the storage space application has been submitted. The following points provide information on the topics to be clarified during the meeting.

3.3.8.1 Need for tamper protection

Reviewers should carefully check whether a high level of tamper protection is absolutely necessary. This should be derived from the justification and always be accompanied by consultation. The reasons why S3 resources cannot meet the need must be explicitly stated.

They must also explain how manipulation protection is ensured before delivery to Coscine. This is necessary to provide complete proof later that the data has not been manipulated.

In many cases, protection against manipulation can be ensured and verified more easily and cost-effectively by using appropriate authorization concepts alongside checksums, certificates and timestamps. Therefore, it is necessary to explain why these measures are insufficient in this specific case.

3.3.8.2 Rights

WORM resources cannot be deleted for at least five years. This is due to the hardware replacement cycle. Applicants must therefore demonstrate that they own all rights to the data, and that they have the right to erasure of personal data pursuant to Art. 17 GDPR does not apply.

3.3.8.3 Persons involved

When using the WORM resource, applicants should be aware that all Coscine Project Owners and Members have the ability to upload files. Project Owners must inform them of the consequences of not being able to delete files. This point must be emphasized during a consultation meeting.

3.3.8.4 Need for functional testing

No test projects are provided for WORM resources. The Coscine functions must be tested in advance using a test project with S3 storage. This procedure must also be emphasized in a consultation.

3.3.9 Workflow and structure

Resource types: S3 and WORM

The key question for reviewers in this section is: 'Is the structure and findability of (meta)data maintained and ensured?' The Coscine-JARDS application asks researchers about their planned workflow at the level of research data and metadata.

At this level, the data delivery process must be described (e.g. via the web interface, the REST API or S3 clients). If automated data delivery processes already exist or are planned, these should be described in the application accordingly. For example, the feature for adding a PDF document to the storage space application can be used to submit a data management plan (DMP). This plan describes how FAIR handling of research data is to be implemented within a research project, and how this will

be realized during the project period. A DMP provides additional support for reviewers and is not a mandatory document for submitting a storage space application.

3.3.9.1 Data flow

Applicants should describe clearly where the files originate (e.g. microscope, literature research, etc.) and how they will be used by Coscine or DataStorage.nrw.

Text Module

Please provide a detailed description of where your files come from, how you currently use them in Coscine, and how you plan to use them in the future. If you have a data management plan for your research project and have not already submitted it with your storage space request, this can also be helpful.

3.3.9.2 Uploading files

Describing data delivery methods (e.g. via the web interface, the REST API or S3 clients) enables reviewers to assess possible metadata management strategies. When selecting 'web interface' or 'REST API', the question arises as to whether an S3 resource is necessary, since web resources are sufficient in this case and can be requested accordingly. After consultation with the researchers, the request is rejected and can be restored, considering the appropriate resources and their use.

Text Module

The reviewers of your storage space application are missing a description of the process for uploading individual files for their assessment. Please briefly explain whether you intend to upload and download the data via the web interface or REST API, or, if you are requesting S3 storage space, via S3 clients. For each of the options you mention, please also provide a brief description of how you intend to implement this in your research project.

3.3.9.3 Data structure and findability

In accordance with FAIR principles, data should be organized and stored in a coordinated manner (e.g. within the research group). Applicants should describe this data structure, i.e. how files are stored and saved, and how they can be retrieved. The search function available in Coscine could be mentioned here, for example.

Text Module

At this stage, the reviewers need to know how you ensure the findability of the files, so that the data can be reused in future.

3.3.9.4 Location of metadata storage

Storing meaningful and rich metadata in accordance with the FAIR principles is one of Coscine's core principles. Therefore, applications for storage space must clearly and explicitly describe how metadata storage will be handled. When using web resources, metadata is entered via the web interface or the REST API. Both options require the selection and completion of a metadata profile when creating the resource, before any files can be uploaded.

For S3 resources, metadata can be stored in various ways. This can be achieved using metadata profiles stored in Coscine, by specifying them in separate readme files, or via automated processes for storing metadata. At this stage, it is crucial that applicants clearly and comprehensively specify the location of the metadata storage for the benefit of reviewers.

Text Module

In terms of the FAIR principles, the storage of metadata relating to research data is a core aspect of Cosine. However, your storage space application does not specify the location of the metadata repository. To give the reviewers a deeper insight into your (planned) metadata management, please describe the following points:

- Will the metadata be stored via Coscine (metadata profiles), or will readme files be used instead?
- Can you provide an example of a readme file?
- Are there automated processes for storing metadata?

3.3.9.5 Metadata annotation workflow

In line with the FAIR principles, submitting metadata for the relevant research data is essential. At this stage, important questions for reviewers are:

- Is it clearly described how the metadata is linked to the research data?
- Is the delivery of the metadata to be via the web interface (as enforced by the metadata profile), or is delivery via S3 planned (in which case a description of the workflow is required)?
- Is the metadata rich (i.e. bibliographic, administrative or technical)?

- Is a metadata profile used in Coscine? If so, which one? Are the mandatory fields in this metadata profile sufficient for the requested storage space? Is it a subject-specific metadata profile?
- Does the metadata profile correspond to the planned reuse of the data? In particular, does it meet the requirements of possible downstream systems, such as research data repositories?

4. Scientific review

Storage space applications exceeding 125 TB require a scientific review of the quality of the research project.¹²

If an application is for a research project that has already been reviewed as part of a related funding program (e.g., a DFG project) and this is documented with a corresponding funding number, an additional scientific review of the storage space application is not necessary. RWTH Aachen University will check that the project description in the application matches the project description on the funding body's website.

If no funding number with a corresponding scientific review is available, a scientific review must be carried out via Coscine-JARDS. For this purpose, a scientific reviewer will be assigned to the application after the technical review. The coordination office at RWTH Aachen University will identify and select a suitable person, using one of the following options:

- 1) Request via the helpdesk of a relevant NFDI consortium.
- 2) Request to persons who have already submitted a storage space application with the same DFG subject class.

¹² Information for Scientific Reviewers (RWTH High Performance Computing (Linux)) - IT Center Help (accessed on January, 12th, 2026)

5. Assessment Checklist

Technical Review	
Contact Information	Text Passage
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who is the submitting Person? (PI) Are they eligible to apply? Is there a connection to the NFDI? If so, to which consortium, and is close supervision provided (e.g., by a data steward)? 	See 3.1.1 Status of applicants
Get an overview of project information	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the project URL work? If storage space is to be distributed across different projects: Are all projects specified with a URL and storage space allocation? 	See 3.2.1 URL
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the storage space requirement described in the application for a research project? 	See 3.2.2 Project relevance
Checking the required storage space allocation	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the requested amount of storage space reasonable in relation to the specified file formats, number of files, etc.? Is a metadata profile specified? If so, is the number of (mandatory) fields reasonable in relation to the amount of storage space? Is the findability of the data ensured? Is the workflow regarding metadata (storage) explained? 	See 3.3.1 Storage Space Scope See 3.3.6 Metadata profiles See 3.3.9 Workflow & Structure See 3.3.9.5 Workflow for metadata annotation
Scientific review	
Review funding for the project	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the project receiving funding? If yes, only perform a technical review. If no, perform a scientific review as described. 	See 4 Scientific review

6. Acknowledgements

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